

Online delivery of pharmacy education: A student center assessment

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Abstract

Online education is a form of education through the internet using electronic devices such as home activities and shifts to online curriculum. Online learning become the new normal due to extraordinary effect of coronavirus. Coronavirus (COVID-19) is a newly discovered virus that affects many countries. The first case of COVID-19 was reported last December 2019 in Wuhan, China. This global pandemic made a huge impact on all the learners and educators as schools and universities shut down to comply with the government's method of slowing down the outbreak and in an attempt to prevent further damage to the whole population. This study aimed to know the response of students to online delivery of pharmacy education. The authors sent out an electronic survey to Pharmacy students at St. Dominic College of Asia. 80 students participated on the study. Descriptive statistics were calculated. Using Likert questions, the following data were obtained: the demographic profile, perceived general feedback, coping mechanism, perceived online barriers, perceived academic support, and perceived students' online academic management. The general feedback of respondents is within the range of 2.49 to 3.49 means neutral and verbally interpreted as fair feedback and the online barriers are sometimes experienced by the respondents. Students also perceived that they received fair academic support. They can also fairly manage online academic priorities. Generally, respondents are well adjusted with online learning.

Keywords: Online education, coronavirus, online learning, global pandemic, online pharmacy education.

To cite this article:

Arro, R., Basada, F., Lozada, H. J., Polvorido, V. K., & Marin, A. R. (2021). Online delivery of pharmacy education: A student center assessment. *The Capsule*, 2, 13-25.

Introduction

The COVID-19 outbreak was first identified in Wuhan, China in December 2019. The outbreak did not only disrupt the world economy, but it also made a huge impact in education system. This global pandemic deeply affects all learners and educators as schools and universities shut down to comply with the government's method of slowing down the outbreak and to prevent further damage to the whole population.

Every country is currently working to implement plans and procedures to contain the virus, but the number of cases continues to rise. In the educational context, the new normal should be considered in the planning and implementation of the new normal educational policy to maintain and offer excellent education despite lockdown and community quarantine (Tria, 2020).

Schools and universities embraced online learning as an alternative way of teaching students while at home. We are no strangers to online learning. In fact, online learning has already been practiced long before the pandemic (Almaghaslah et al., 2018; Chiampas et al., 2018; Hamilton et al., 2016; Lorenzani et al., 2019). This type of learning was used by students and other learners who cannot attend a physical classroom due to different factors such as distance, health issues, and inclement weather, among others. Most students and educators are familiar with this method of learning since this is one of the best alternative ways of teaching.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive type of research and a quantitative approach. Researchers used the survey to gather data about varying subjects.

Sample

Table 1. Demographic profile of respondents

Demographic Profile		Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Year Level	First Year	21	26	2
	Second Year	17	21	4
	Third Year	18	23	3
	Fourth Year	24	30	1
Age	23 and above	18	23	2
	18 to 22	62	78	1
Monthly Income	Above Php 78,900.00	12	15	4
	Php 31,560.00 - 78,900.00	18	23	3
	Php 15,780.00 - 31,560.00	21	26	2
	Below Php 15,780.00	29	36	1
Device Use	Desktop computer / Laptop	46	58	1
	Mobile Phone	34	43	2
Type of Internet Connection	Mobile data	21	26	3
	PLDT, Converge, etc.	28	35	2
	Wi-Fi	31	39	1
Data Capacity	Unlimited Data	19	24	3
	Limited data	38	48	1
	No Response	23	29	2
Total		80	100	

The table above shows the demographic profile of respondents. For Year Level, out of 80 respondents; 21 or 26 percent are first-year, 17 or 21 percent are second-year, 18 or 23 percent are the third year and 24 or 30 percent are fourth-year. For age, 18 or 23 percent are respondents whose ages fall within 23 and above, and 62 or 78 percent are respondents whose ages fall within 18 to 22 years old. For monthly income, 12 or 15 percent are respondents with a monthly income of above Php 78,900.00, 18 or 23 percent are respondents with a monthly income of Php 31,560.00 – 78,900.00, 21 or 26 percent are respondents with a monthly income of Php 15,780.00 – 31,560.00, and 29 or 36 percent are respondents with a monthly income of below Php 15,780.00. For device use, 46 or 58 percent of the respondents are using a desktop computer / laptop, and 34 or 43 percent of the respondents are using a mobile phone. For the type of internet connection, 21 or 26 percent of the respondents are using mobile data, 28 or 35 percent of the respondents are using PLDT and Converge, and 31 or 39 percent of the respondents are using Wi-Fi. For data capacity, 19 or 24 percent of the respondents are using unlimited data, 38 or 48 percent are using limited data. However, 23 or 29 percent of the respondents did not respond.

Sampling Procedures

To get respondents who will participate in this study, the researchers used convenience non-probability sampling. Convenience sampling is a sort of nonprobability sampling in which participants are randomly selected because they are "convenient" sources of data for researchers.

Instruments

This study utilized a 36-item 5-point Likert scale survey questionnaire. Items 1, 6, 11, 16, 21, 26, 31, 36, 41, and 46 are items that measure General Feedback. Items 2, 7, 12, 17, 22, 27, 32, 37, 42, and 47 are items that measure online barriers. Items 3, 8, 13, 18, 23, 28, 33, 38, 43, and 48 are items that measure perceived academic support. Items 4, 9, 14, 19, 24, 29, 34, 39, 44, and 49 are items that measure student's online academic management. Items 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, and 50 are items that measure coping mechanisms.

The survey questionnaire underwent validation and reliability scoring with subject matter experts. The Cronbach's alpha for General Feedback is 0.936. The Cronbach's alpha for Online Barriers is 0.879. The Cronbach's alpha for Perceived Academic Support is 0.841. The Cronbach's alpha for Student's Online Academic Management is 0.853. The Cronbach's alpha for Coping Mechanism is 0.955. The overall Cronbach's alpha is .981.

Data Analysis

The following statistics were used to conduct data analysis:

Frequency. This was used to get the number of respondents classified based on the sub-level of each demographic profile.

Mean. This is to get the mean scores of factors such as General Feedback, Online Barrier, Perceived Academic Support, Student Online Academic Management, and Coping Mechanism

Percentage. This refers to the proportion or representation of a specific sub-level of a demographic profile.

T-Test for Independent Samples. This is to get a significant difference between the two (2) groups.

One-Way Analysis of Variance. This is to get a significant difference for more than two (2) groups.

Table 2. Reference Scale for General Feedback

Rating Scale	Arbitrary Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Good Feedback in Online Education
4	3.50-4.49	Agree	Good Feedback in Online Education
3	2.50-3.49	Neutral	Fair Feedback in Online Education
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree	Needs Improvement Feedback in Online Education
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree	Poor Feedback in Online Education

Table 3. Reference Scale for Perceived Academic Support

Rating Scale	Arbitrary Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Good Academic Support
4	3.50-4.49	Agree	Good Academic Support
3	2.50-3.49	Neutral	Fair Academic Support
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree	Poor Academic Support
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree	Very Poor Academic Support

Table 4. Reference Scale for Online Barriers

Rating Scale	Arbitrary Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree	Always experience online barriers
4	3.50-4.49	Agree	Often experience online barriers
3	2.50-3.49	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree	Rarely experience online barriers
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree	Never experience online barriers

Table 5. Reference Scale for Student Academic Management

Rating Scale	Arbitrary Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Good Online Management
4	3.50-4.49	Agree	Good Online Management
3	2.50-3.49	Neutral	Fair Online Management
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree	Poor Online Management
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree	Very Poor Online Management

Table 6. Reference Scale for Coping Mechanism

Rating Scale	Arbitrary Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Well Adjusted with Online Learning
4	3.50-4.49	Agree	Well Adjusted with Online Learning
3	2.50-3.49	Neutral	Fair Adjustments with Online Learning
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree	Poor Adjustments in Online Learning
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree	Very Poor Adjustments in Online Learning

Results and Discussion

Table 7. Mean Score for General Feedback on Online Education

Demographic Profile	Mean	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation	
Year Level	First Year	3.31	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
	Second Year	3.06	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
	Third Year	3.06	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
	Fourth Year	3.08	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
Age	23 and above	3.11	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
	18 to 22	3.14	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
Monthly Income	Above Php 78,900.00	2.88	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
	Php 31,560.00 - 78,900.00	3.38	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
	Php 15,780.00 - 31,560.00	3.05	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
	Below Php 15,780.00	3.14	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
Device Use	Desktop computer / Laptop	3.24	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
	Mobile Phone	2.99	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
Type of Internet Connection	Mobile data	3.32	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
	PLDT, Converge, etc.	3.13	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
	Wi-Fi	3.01	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
Data Capacity	Unlimited Data	3.25	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
	Limited data	3.23	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
	No Response	2.88	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education
Total	3.13	Neutral	Fair Feedback on Online Education	

The table above shows the mean score for general feedback in online education across demographic profiles. Results show that across demographic profile (Year Level, Age, Monthly Income, Device Use, Type of Network Connection and Data Capacity), the computed mean is with the range of

2.49 to 3.49, which is verbally described as “Neutral” and verbally interpreted as “Fair Feedback on Online Education”.

Table 8. Mean Score for Barriers on Online Education

Demographic Profile		Mean	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
Year Level	First Year	3.28	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
	Second Year	3.03	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
	Third Year	3.27	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
	Fourth Year	3.24	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
Age	23 and above	3.00	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
	18 to 22	3.27	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
Monthly Income	Above Php 78,900.00	3.28	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
	Php 31,560.00 - 78,900.00	3.28	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
	Php 15,780.00 - 31,560.00	3.31	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
	Below Php 15,780.00	3.07	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
Device Use	Desktop computer / Laptop	3.34	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
	Mobile Phone	3.04	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
Type of Internet Connection	Mobile data	3.13	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
	PLDT, Converge, etc.	3.36	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
	Wi-Fi	3.13	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
Data Capacity	Unlimited Data	3.16	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
	Limited data	3.37	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
	No Response	2.99	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers
Total		3.21	Neutral	Sometimes experience online barriers

The table above shows the mean score for online barriers in online education across demographic profiles. Results showed that across demographic profile (Year Level, Age, Monthly Income, Device Use, Type of Network Connection and Data Capacity), the computed mean is with the range of 2.49 to 3.49, which is verbally described as “Neutral” and verbally interpreted as “Sometimes experience online barriers”.

Coronavirus pandemic made a huge impact on online education. School cannot run the traditional face-to-face class; the government established an online learning system. Online education can be an advantage or disadvantage. There are many barriers that can affect online education. Some of the problems that students might encounter are internet connection and other technical issues (unstable network, audio, and visual problems) like gadgets to use for online learning, playing online games, social media platforms distractions, and problems focusing due to house chores (Ali et al., 2021; Epp, 2021; Kawaguchi-Suzuki et al., 2020). Respondents provided a neutral response to barriers of online education that has a means core that ranges between 2.49 to 3.49 which is verbally described as “neutral”.

A study was conducted about barriers to online learning in the time of COVID-19 as a national survey of medical students in the Philippines. This study focused on how the medical students are coping with the sudden shift of way of learning. Some of the students experience having a problem with the gadgets used internet connection and power interruptions. Given the striking finding is that students did not perceive these technological limitations to be the most important barriers. This shows that students have somehow managed to cope with these challenges during the global pandemic (Baticulon, 2020).

Table 9. Mean Score for Perceived Academic Support in Online Education

Demographic Profile		Mean	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
Year Level	First Year	3.37	Neutral	Fair Academic Support
	Second Year	3.34	Neutral	Fair Academic Support
	Third Year	3.32	Neutral	Fair Academic Support
	Fourth Year	3.25	Neutral	Fair Academic Support
Age	23 and above	3.39	Neutral	Fair Academic Support
	18 to 22	3.29	Neutral	Fair Academic Support
Monthly Income	Above Php 78,900.00	2.88	Neutral	Fair Academic Support
	Php 31,560.00 - 78,900.00	3.54	Agree	Good Academic Support
	Php 15,780.00 - 31,560.00	3.21	Neutral	Fair Academic Support
	Below Php 15,780.00	3.42	Neutral	Fair Academic Support
Device Use	Desktop computer / Laptop	3.44	Neutral	Fair Academic Support
	Mobile Phone	3.14	Neutral	Fair Academic Support
Type of Internet Connection	Mobile data	3.63	Agree	Good Academic Support
	PLDT, Converge, etc.	3.28	Neutral	Fair Academic Support
	Wi-Fi	3.13	Neutral	Fair Academic Support
Data Capacity	Unlimited Data	3.31	Neutral	Fair Academic Support
	Limited data	3.46	Neutral	Fair Academic Support
	No Response	3.08	Neutral	Fair Academic Support
Total		3.31	Neutral	Fair Academic Support

The table above shows the mean score for Perceived Academic Support in online education across demographic profiles. Results showed that across demographic profile (Year Level, Age, Monthly Income, Device Use, Type of Network Connection, and Data Capacity), the computed mean is with the range of 2.49 to 3.49, which is verbally described as “Neutral” and verbally interpreted as “Fair Academic Support”. Except for 31,560.00 - 78,900.00 monthly income and Mobile data as Type of Network Connection, the computed mean is with the range of 3.49 to 4.50, which is verbally described as “Agree” and verbally interpreted as “Good Academic Support”.

Results show that across a demographic profile for academic support (year level, age, monthly income, device use, type of network connection, and data capacity) the overall perceived academic support is verbally interpreted as ‘fair academic support with online learning’. Students were provided by their professors with different learning materials such as recorded videos of lectures and soft copy of lessons for them to study. Overall, students are satisfied with the academic support that they are getting from their professors. They were given different learning materials to use for studying and as a reference for their homework (Verdone et al., 2020). Educators are doing their part to make sure that students can learn at home by providing different resources that students can use. This is evidently shown on the result for Perceived Academic Support in online education that has a mean score that ranges between 2.49 to 3.49 which is described as "Neutral".

As indicated in CHED Memorandum Order No. 04 Series of 2020, the design and delivery of programs, courses, and learning interventions address learners’ unique needs in terms of place, pace, process, and products of learning. It involves the use of digital and non-digital technology and covers both face-to-face on in-person learning, out-of-classroom learning modes of delivery or a combination of modes of delivery (De Vera, 2020).

Table 10. Mean Score for Student Academic Management in Online Education

Demographic Profile		Mean	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
Year Level	First Year	3.13	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
	Second Year	3.04	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
	Third Year	3.33	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
	Fourth Year	3.17	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
Age	23 and above	3.32	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
	18 to 22	3.13	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
Monthly Income	Above Php 78,900.00	3.10	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
	Php 31,560.00 - 78,900.00	3.49	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
	Php 15,780.00 - 31,560.00	2.89	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
	Below Php 15,780.00	3.21	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
Device Use	Desktop computer / Laptop	3.25	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
	Mobile Phone	3.06	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
Type of Internet Connection	Mobile data	3.22	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
	PLDT, Converge, etc.	3.24	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
	Wi-Fi	3.08	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
Data Capacity	Unlimited Data	3.28	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
	Limited data	3.23	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
	No Response	2.97	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management
Total		3.17	Neutral	Fair Online Academic Management

The table above shows the mean score for Student Online Academic Engagement in online education across demographic profiles. Results showed that across demographic profile (Year Level, Age, Monthly Income, Device Use, Type of Network Connection and Data Capacity), the computed mean is with the range of 2.49 to 3.49, which is verbally described as “Neutral” and verbally interpreted as “Fair Online Academic Management”. The result showed that across demographic profiles (year level, age, monthly income, device uses, type of network connection, and data capacity) the overall academic management in online education is verbally interpreted as fair online academic management.

Most common problems that students encounter during this pandemic is the way they learn or study their lesson on their own. While this may seem convenient because it gives students freedom to study at their own pace, this has also tolerated them to procrastinate (Altwaijry et al., 2020). Respondents provide a neutral response regarding their own academic management. Choices that are related to student academic management are settings goals to effectively learn, quality of work, summarizing what they have learned, making thorough notes, finding a comfortable place to study, avoiding distractions, and getting help from others. The neutral response from the students only means that students are not consistent when it comes to their own academic management. They did not completely agree with the different managing techniques that they can use in order to effectively learn during this pandemic. A neutral response also means that the students are struggling to learn on their own because of different distractions from home. In a traditional classroom set-up, it is hard not to focus on a class or do your classwork in time because teachers are present to constantly remind the student to listen to their lessons and submit their work on time. At home, no one is in charge but their own self that is why self-discipline is more important. Neutral responses regarding student’s academic management are evidently shown in the result. Mean score ranges between 3.49 to 4.49, which is verbally described as “neutral”.

According to Northeastern University a private research university in Boston, Massachusetts, despite the flexibility in being an online student, it is important to have frequent engagement with studies throughout the week. Provide plenty of time to space out the required readings, assignments, and online discussions. Multitasking should be avoided as well because it can decrease your productivity. Focus on one assignment at a time and concentrate at hand, whether this is studying for an exam, reading a textbook, emailing a professor, or engaging in an online discussion board. Make sure there is a high-speed

internet, and that you are in a comfortable space with the right lighting, sound, and background. Make sure you are not spending too much time on the internet. When you need to concentrate on your academics, stay concentrated and ignore Facebook, Twitter, and other social media platforms. To prevent burnout, it is critical to praise oneself for a job well done. It will be tough to focus on even the simplest chores if this is not done. Apart from rewarding yourself, finding a balance between academics and other duties is critical, especially if you are juggling school and job. Finally, make sure you receive a decent night's sleep. Sleep is necessary for your body to rest and your intellect to be refreshed for the next day (Miller, 2020).

Table 11. Mean Score for Coping Mechanism in Online Education

Demographic Profile		Mean	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
Year Level	First Year	3.45	Neutral	Fair Adjustments with Online Learning
	Second Year	3.36	Neutral	Fair Adjustments with Online Learning
	Third Year	3.82	Agree	Well Adjusted with Online Learning
	Fourth Year	3.46	Neutral	Fair Adjustments with Online Learning
Age	23 and above	3.63	Agree	Well Adjusted with Online Learning
	18 to 22	3.48	Neutral	Fair Adjustments with Online Learning
Monthly Income	Above Php 78,900.00	3.41	Neutral	Fair Adjustments with Online Learning
	Php 31,560.00 - 78,900.00	3.78	Agree	Well Adjusted with Online Learning
	Php 15,780.00 - 31,560.00	3.28	Neutral	Fair Adjustments with Online Learning
	Below Php 15,780.00	3.57	Agree	Well Adjusted with Online Learning
Device Use	Desktop computer / Laptop	3.57	Agree	Well Adjusted with Online Learning
	Mobile Phone	3.45	Neutral	Fair Adjustments with Online Learning
Type of Internet Connection	Mobile data	3.77	Agree	Well Adjusted with Online Learning
	PLDT, Converge, etc.	3.44	Neutral	Fair Adjustments with Online Learning
	Wi-Fi	3.42	Neutral	Fair Adjustments with Online Learning
Data Capacity	Unlimited Data	3.63	Agree	Well Adjusted with Online Learning
	Limited data	3.68	Agree	Well Adjusted with Online Learning
	No Response	3.16	Neutral	Fair Adjustments with Online Learning
Total		3.52	Agree	Well Adjusted with Online Learning

The table above shows the mean score for Coping Mechanisms in online education across demographic profiles. Results showed that the overall Coping Mechanism across demographic profiles (Year Level, Age, Monthly Income, Device Use, Type of Network Connection and Data Capacity), the computed mean is within the range of 3.49 to 4.49, which is verbally described as “Agree” and verbally interpreted as “Well Adjusted with Online Learning”.

Results show that across demographic profiles, the overall coping mechanism of the students is verbally interpreted as well adjusted with online learning. Respondents were able to cope with stress by doing different activities and managing their online learning difficulties by using different styles and techniques on how they can improve themselves same as their skills and knowledge while at home.

While adopting the new normal, students somehow managed to help themselves during this pandemic. This is evidently shown on the result for coping mechanism in online education that has a mean score that ranges between 3.49 to 4.49 which is verbally described as "Agree".

According to Uzzaman and Karim (2017) as cited in Chandra (2021), in a research "Emotional Intelligence Scale: Assessing its Psychometric Characteristics in Bangladeshi Culture", it was observed that respondents were able to reduce negative and unexpected emotional outbursts and were able to divert them into different activities knowingly or unknowingly which is one of the coping strategies adopted by students.

Table 12. Test for Significant Difference for Year Level Demographic Profile Across Factors

Factors	p-value	Significance	Ho Decision
General Feedback	0.789	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Online Barrier	0.818	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Perceived Academic Support	0.985	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Student Online Academic Management	0.849	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Coping Mechanism	0.511	Not Significant	Failed to Reject

*Significant at .05 alpha level

The table above shows the test for significant difference for year level. Across all factors (General Feedback, Online Barrier, Perceived Academic Support, Student Online Academic Management, and Coping Mechanism), the computed p-value is greater than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference in mean score across all factors assessed based on the year level and null hypothesis failed to reject.

Table 13. Test for Significant Difference for Age Demographic Profile Across Factors

Factors	p-value	Significance	Ho Decision
General Feedback	0.919	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Online Barrier	0.267	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Perceived Academic Support	0.738	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Student Online Academic Management	0.496	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Coping Mechanism	0.608	Not Significant	Failed to Reject

*Significant at .05 alpha level

The table above shows the test for significant difference for age. Across all factors (General Feedback, Online Barrier, Perceived Academic Support, Student Online Academic Management, and Coping Mechanism), the computed p-value is greater than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference in mean score across all factors assessed based on age and null hypothesis failed to reject.

Table 14. Test for Significant Difference for Monthly Income Demographic Profile Across Factors

Factors	p-value	Significance	Ho Decision
General Feedback	0.484	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Online Barrier	0.757	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Perceived Academic Support	0.365	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Student Online Academic Management	0.289	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Coping Mechanism	0.413	Not Significant	Failed to Reject

*Significant at .05 alpha level

The table above shows the test for monthly income. Across all factors (General Feedback, Online Barrier, Perceived Academic Support, Student Online Academic Management, and Coping Mechanism), the computed p-value is greater than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference in mean score across all factors assessed based on monthly income and null hypothesis failed to reject.

Table 15. Test for Significant Difference for Device Use Demographic Profile Across Factors

Factors	p-value	Significance	Ho Decision
General Feedback	0.231	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Online Barrier	0.139	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Perceived Academic Support	0.208	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Student Online Academic Management	0.403	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Coping Mechanism	0.608	Not Significant	Failed to Reject

*Significant at .05 alpha level

The table above shows the test for significant difference for device use. Across all factors (General Feedback, Online Barrier, Perceived Academic Support, Student Online Academic Management, and Coping Mechanism), the computed p-value is greater than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference in mean score across all factors assessed based on the device use and null hypothesis failed to reject.

Table 16. Test for Significant Difference for Internet Connection Demographic Profile Across Factors

Factors	p-value	Significance	Ho Decision
General Feedback	0.482	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Online Barrier	0.557	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Perceived Academic Support	0.243	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Student Online Academic Management	0.800	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Coping Mechanism	0.394	Not Significant	Failed to Reject

*Significant at .05 alpha level

The table above shows the test for Type of Internet Connection. Across all factors (General Feedback, Online Barrier, Perceived Academic Support, Student Online Academic Management, and Coping Mechanism), the computed p-value is greater than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference in mean score across all factors assessed based on the internet connection and null hypothesis failed to reject.

Table 17. Test for Significant Difference for Data Capacity Demographic Profile Across Factors

Factors	p-value	Significance	Ho Decision
General Feedback	0.289	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Online Barrier	0.247	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Perceived Academic Support	0.418	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Student Online Academic Management	0.506	Not Significant	Failed to Reject
Coping Mechanism	0.104	Not Significant	Failed to Reject

*Significant at .05 alpha level

The table above shows the test for Data Capacity demographic profile. Across all factors (General Feedback, Online Barrier, Perceived Academic Support, Student Online Academic Management, and Coping Mechanism), the computed p-value is greater than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference in mean score across all factors assessed based on the data capacity and null hypothesis failed to reject.

Conclusion and Recommendations

COVID-19 pandemic has changed the way how people receive and impart education. We hesitate in accepting any change in delivering education because we are used to traditional methods of teaching such as face-to-face lectures (Salari et al., 2021). We are forced to transition to the new normal of delivering education because we have no other alternative left other than accepting the change and adapting to online delivery of education. This pandemic taught us that we need to be ready to face challenges (Bartolo et al., 2020; Shawaqfeh et al., 2020).

The research study shows that unstable internet connection is the primary concerns of students in their online academic learning. Being engaged in social media, technical issues and outdoor noise distracts students in their online learning. In SDCA online academic engagement, Blackboard as asynchronous learning and zoom as online synchronous learning is utilized as online learning platforms by respondents. In student's online engagement, most of the online learning materials shared with them are lectures in PDF and PowerPoint presentations and self-recorded lectures. Quizzes and examinations are primarily used as assessments in students' online learning. The general feedback of respondents is fair or average feedback and online barriers are sometimes experienced by the respondents. Respondents perceived that they received fair or average academic support. They can also fairly manage their online academic priorities. Generally, respondents are well adjusted to online learning.

Recommendations were listed below from the study:

- Students must use their time wisely to effectively learn while at home.
- As much as possible stay away from distractions such as social media that hinder you from studying or finishing homework.
- Ask for help if necessary. Ask questions for clarifications in case you are having trouble understanding the lesson.
- Students must find different styles or techniques on how they can learn and study on their own.
- Students must focus on studying and completing their school activities first before engaging in other activities not related to school. Social media and television can divert students' attention, and this consumes a lot of time. This can affect them from finishing their homework on time.
- Students should stay resourceful and diligent in their task.
- Evaluate yourself and be honest whether you truly understand and learn or not and find ways on how you can improve yourself this pandemic.
- Find a comfortable spot to study. Secure a space at home where you can easily work on your homework and other activities without any distractions. Use this space as your study area.
- Reward yourself after a job well done to avoid burnout or stress. Keep yourself healthy by getting enough sleep, rest, and exercise. A healthy body and mind are very important especially in this pandemic.
- Different learning materials must be provided to students so that they can easily understand the lessons.
- For educators, provide exercises, homework, and other activities to practice their skills and knowledge as a future pharmacist. Activities/exercises must fit well to student's need, especially in their future profession.
- Make every online class more interactive, fun, and engage in learning effectively. This is to keep the student's attention in class and focus on the lessons.

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